

Supplementary Material

Conflict over the eukaryote root resides in strong outliers, mosaics and missing data sensitivity of site-specific (CAT) mixture models

Caesar Al Jewari & Sandra Baldauf

Figure S1a. Multiple sequence alignment showing regions highlighted in yellow with too many gaps that trimal -gappy out did not remove, those sites are manually trimmed in core1 dataset preparation.

Figure S1b. Multiple sequence alignment showing regions highlighted in yellow that trimal -gappyout removed in full_data, those sites were retained in core1 dataset preparation.

Figure S2. Internode certainty (ICA) scores for selected splits in the full mitoP data. ICA scores were calculated for each locus of the full mitoP dataset (76 loci, 180 taxa) using 100 bootstrap trees (Salichos and Rokas 2013) as implemented in RAxML 8.2.12 (Stamatakis, 2014). The top three rows represent the three alternative hypotheses for the first split in eukaryotes (AMO: Amorphea, DIA: Diaphoreticketes, DSC: Discoba). Positive and negative IC scores are emphasized using green and red bars, respectively.

Figure S3. Inter node certainty (ICA) scores for selected splits in the mitoP core-1 data set. ICA scores for the reduced mitoP data set used for ConWin analyses (76 loci, 70 taxa) were calculated using 100 bootstrap trees (Salichos and Rokas 2013) as implemented in RAXML 8.2.12 (Stamatakis, 2014). The top three rows represent the three alternative hypotheses for the first split in eukaryotes (AMO: Amorphea, DIA: Diaphoretickes, DSC: Discoba). Positive and negative ICA scores are indicated using green and red bars, respectively

Figure S4. Internode certainty (ICA) scores for selected splits in 1976 ConJak subsamples of 14 proteins each from the 76 mitoP proteins. The ICA values in each column is based on the 364 subsample trees in which the given protein occurs (x axis). The ICA score was calculated according to Salichos and Rokas (2013) as implemented in RAxML 8.2.12 (Stamatakis, 2014). The top three rows represent the three alternative hypotheses for the first split in eukaryotes (AMO: Amorphea, DIA: Diaphoretickes, DSC: Discoba). Positive and negative IC scores are indicated using green and red bars, respectively.

Figure S5. Depth of taxon sampling in GenBank versus phylogenetic tree stability. The numbers on the log scaled x-axis were extracted from GenBank taxonomy (Benson et al. 2013; Schoch et al. 2020) on Aug 2020. The y-axis shows the stability scores per major taxon group calculated from analysis of 76 mitochondrial proteins using ConJak with a 20% truncated mean per group. Stability scores are plotted against values derived from GenBank Taxonomy database for a) number of phylogenetic nodes with sequence data, b) total number of protein sequences and c) total number of genomes.

Figure S6. ConWin sliding window analysis of potential mosaicism in mtHsp60 protein 40 (mtHsp60) in Discoba. The 522 amino acid alignment was divided into seven equal-length chops, which were then paired to create six consecutive 50%-overlapping sliding windows of 148 amino acids each. The trees shown were derived by analysis of the full-length alignment (full) and windows 1-5 (w1-w5). Trees were inferred using IQTree LG+G4 with Ufast bootstrap support optimized with the -bnni option.

Figure S7. Sliding window analysis of potential mosaicism in heterolobosean mtOP 03 (mtHsp70). The 581 amino acid alignment was divided into seven chops, which were then assembled into six 50% overlapping sliding windows. The figure shows trees based on a) the full alignment including all Discoba, b) the full alignment with only Heterolobosea, and c) sliding window 3, also for only Heterolobosea. In all cases, the full-length alignment was used for all non-discobid taxa. Trees were inferred using IQTree LG+G4 with UF bootstrap support optimized with the -bnni option.

Figure S8. Present versus missing data for Discoba in ConWin core-1 versus core-2 data sets. Core-1 consists of the full 76 mitoP proteins, from which core-2 was created by deleting the 16 discobid-poor proteins shown on the right of the figure. The proportion of filled cells is indicated in blue (Data) and empty cells in grey (Gaps). Components A and B show the proportion of filled cells for discobid data in core-1 versus core-2 respectively, and components C and D show the proportion of empty discobid cells in core-1 versus core-2, respectively.

Figure S9. Phylobayes CAT-GTR analysis of 54 mitoP proteins (core-1) masked for potential mosaics (data set “CW core-1”, Fig. 6). The core-1 data set consists of 58 phylogenetically stable (core) taxa plus 12 test taxa from supergroup Discoba. The 54 mitoP proteins masked for potentially incongruent gene fragments (PIKs) using the program ConWin. The tree shown is based on 22031 aligned amino acid positions using Bayesian inference and the CAT-GTR model implemented in Phylobayes-MPI. Numbers on branches indicate posterior probabilities calculated from two independent search chains each run for 10000 generations. The tree is drawn to scale according to the scale bar at the bottom (substitutions per site).

Figure S10. Full mitoP data masked for strong outliers and analysed using the C60 among-site mixture model (“CJ full-data”, Fig. 6). The tree is based on 66 mitoP proteins masked for strong outliers using the ConJak protocol for a total of 27143 aligned AA position. The tree was inferred using maximum likelihood under the C60+LG+G4+F model using IQTREE. Number to the right and left of the slash (/) indicate bootstrap support values from IQTree C60+LG+G4+F+PMSF and RAXML LG+G, respectively. Branches without values have 100% support from both models. The tree is drawn to scale according to the scale bar at the bottom (substitutions per site).

Figure S11. RAxML LG+G4 phylogeny based on core-2 mitoP proteins masked for potential mosaics (PIKs) (“CW core-2”, Fig. 6). The tree was derived by maximum likelihood analysis of 22031 aligned AA position in 54 proteins under the LG+G4 model implemented in RAXML-NG. The numbers on branches are support percentages of 100 standard bootstrap trees inferred under the same model. The core-2 dataset is a reduced version of core-1 with 16 proteins with excessive missing data removed.

Figure S12. The core-2 subset of 54n mitopP proteins masked for potential mosaics (PIKs) and analyzed using the C60 among site mixture model (“CW core-2, Fig. 6). Phylogeny is based on 22031 aligned amino acid positions in 54 proteins with minimal missing data for *Discoba* (core-2). The tree was inferred using Maximum Likelihood under the C60+LG+G4+F model implemented in IQTree. The numbers on branches are bootstrap percentages inferred using the PMSF approximate model to C60+LG+G4+F model on the left and UFB+bnni on the right. The core-2 dataset is a reduced version pf core-1 with 16 proteins with excessive missing data removed.